

IMPROVING INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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Foreign language is one of the basic tools of education of individuals with planetary thinking. Foreign language as the means of international communication can foster students' bilingual social competence, including the formation of such qualities as tolerance, open-mindedness towards other cultures, peoples and countries. Studying the language and culture of another people, students have the opportunity to expand their social-cultural knowledge. Linguists and anthropologists have long recognized that the forms and uses of a given language reflect the cultural values of the society in which the language is spoken. Linguistic competence alone is not enough for learners of a language to be competent in that language [1]. Language learners need to be aware, for example, of the culturally appropriate ways to address people, express gratitude, make requests, and agree or disagree with someone.

There has been developed a system of levels of language proficiency and the system of description of these levels using the standard categories. These two complexes provide a network of concepts, which can be used to describe any certification system and any training program in a standard language, starting with setting goals and ending attainable resulted competencies [2].

The developed specifications for the foreign language teaching are based on the main principles which are level approach to the presenting linguistic-didactic items and communicative-oriented approach to the selection of educational material content. The process of the formation of the text at the level of sentences, that is

grammar and vocabulary, is considered not as an educational goal but as means for communication purposes.

The study and use of a foreign language include human's actions developing a number of competences: General competence and Communicative language competence. The competence is referred as the amount of knowledge, skills and personal qualities that allow a person to perform different actions.

General competences include: ability to learn; existential competence; declarative knowledge; skills and know-how. General competences are not linguistic ones, they mean any activity, including communicative one.

Communicative language competence includes: linguistic components (lexical, phonological, syntactical knowledge and skills); social-linguistic component; pragmatic component (knowledge, existential competence and skills and know-how relating to the linguistic system and its sociolinguistic variation) and allows to carry out activities with the use of linguistic resources.

There are following components of communicative competence:

1) Grammatical or formal competence or linguistic competence is systematic knowledge of grammar, vocabulary and phonetics units, which convert the lexical items into a statement.

2) Social-linguistic competence is the ability to select and use appropriate language forms and tools depending on the purpose and the situation of communication, social roles of participants of the communication process.

3) The Discursive competence (discourse competence) is the ability to build integrated, coherent and logical expressions of different functional styles in speech and writing, based on understanding the different kinds of texts for reading and listening, involves the choice of linguistic means, depending on the type of utterance.

4) Social-cultural competence is knowledge of the cultural characteristics of native speakers, their habits, traditions, ethics and etiquette and the ability to understand and use them properly in the process of communication. The formation of social competence involves the integration of personality in the worldwide and national cultures.

There have been two main approaches in the history of foreign language teaching: a) the study of language based on the rules, and b) the study of language-based communication.

The first approach is conducted with the help of grammar-translation system in the process of foreign languages teaching. According to it, the process of teaching is based on the study of grammar and vocabulary with the next generation of the transition to the formation and decoding of the speech (reading and understanding spoken speech). The second approach is performed through communication. It is considered more effective, although contains a number of disadvantages. Lack of awareness of the foreign language rules both extends the process of study and reduces the quality of the foreign-language speech.

As a result, there has been a convergence of these two approaches of teaching a foreign language. That is, the unity of language rules and actions has been experimentally proved. The main action being developed with the help of a foreign language is a communication process, or speech communication. In the process of communication there is not only an exchange of views and feelings, but also the development of linguistic resources. Language rules perform an auxiliary function showing the use of linguistic phenomena in speech.

Thus, a foreign language can be considered as a means of developing communicative competence. This means the ability to adequately clothe communication goals and strategies of their achievement into proper language forms, as well as the ability to use the rules of speech etiquette and social behavior in the situations of intercultural communication, where updated knowledge of the situational and social-cultural contexts is actual.

References.

1. Holló, D. & Lázár, I. (2000). The neglected element – Teaching culture in the EFL classroom. *NovELTy*, 7/1.
2. Krasner D. *Defending the national Interest*. 1978
3. Myron W. *Intercultural Competence*. 2012
4. Malika Maxmud kizi Xakimova CULTURAL FEATURES OF VERBAL EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK COMMUNICATION <https://worldofresearch.ru/index.php/wsjc/issue/view/7>